

Approximating the Shapley Value with Many Players: A Hybrid Exact/Monte Carlo Estimator

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April 28, 2026

Abstract

Computing the Shapley value exactly requires evaluating $v(\cdot)$ over all 2^n coalitions, which is intractable for $n \gtrsim 25$. This paper addresses the question of how to draw coalitions efficiently when exact computation is infeasible. We establish a level-stratified framework that clarifies the variance ordering of all existing drawing strategies, and propose two new estimators. The **Hybrid Exact/Sampling estimator** enumerates coalition-size levels with few coalitions exactly and samples only the large middle levels, achieving strictly lower variance than any purely stochastic method. The **Neyman optimal-allocation variant** minimises variance when within-level dispersion is heterogeneous. A unified comparative analysis covers the full spectrum of current methods: permutation sampler (Castro et al., 2009), level-stratified sampler (Maleki et al., 2013), KernelSHAP family (Lundberg & Lee, 2017; Covert & Lee, 2021; Olsen & Jullum, 2025), Owen/antithetic samplers (KhademSohi et al., 2025), and the non-asymptotic framework of Chen et al. (NeurIPS 2025). The bounded marginal impact index $C(v)$ precisely characterises the conditions under which each method dominates. For the broad class of pseudo-continuous functions ($C \ll n$), the hybrid reduces RMSE by 36–92% over the permutation sampler and one to two orders of magnitude over KernelSHAP at equal computational cost.

Keywords

Shapley value; large games; Monte Carlo approximation; stratified sampling; hybrid exact/sampling estimator; KernelSHAP; Owen sampling; Neyman allocation; bounded marginal impact; non-asymptotic sample complexity.

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1 Introduction

1.1 The computational challenge

The Shapley value assigns to each player k their average marginal contribution across all orderings of $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, n\}$, and is the unique allocation satisfying efficiency, symmetry, linearity, and the null-player axiom (Shapley, 1953). Exact computation requires 2^n evaluations of v :

Players n	Subsets 2^n	Exact feasible?	Approx. needed?
10	1,024	Yes (ms)	No
20	1,048,576	Yes (~ 30 s)	Optional
25	33,554,432	Borderline	Recommended
30	1,073,741,824	No (> 1 h)	Yes
50+	$> 10^{15}$	Impossible	Mandatory

Real applications regularly involve $n \geq 30$: SHAP feature importance (Lundberg and Lee, 2017), inequality decompositions (Shorrocks, 2013), and federated learning client valuation (KhademSohi et al., 2025). The question of *which drawing strategy minimises error at fixed computational budget* has attracted intense recent interest, yet no unified comparison exists.

1.2 Contributions

1. **Level-stratified framework** (Section 2): establishes the variance ordering of all drawing strategies and introduces the *bounded marginal impact index* $C(v)$ that governs efficiency.
2. **Hybrid Exact/Sampling estimator** (Section 3): enumerates extreme levels exactly, samples middle levels. Provably lower variance than all purely stochastic methods.
3. **Neyman optimal allocation** (Section 4): minimises variance when $\sigma_k^2(j)$ is heterogeneous; validated on a function with a sharp interaction spike.
4. **Unified comparative analysis** (Section 5): all major methods — permutation, level-stratified, Owen, KernelSHAP family, non-asymptotic bounds (Chen et al., 2025) — compared in a single section on equal footing.

2 Framework: Level-Stratified Decomposition

Definition 1 (Shapley value).

$$e_k = \sum_{\substack{S \subseteq \mathcal{N} \\ k \notin S}} \frac{s!(n-s-1)!}{n!} \text{mv}(S, k), \quad \text{mv}(S, k) = v(S \cup \{k\}) - v(S). \quad (1)$$

Grouping coalitions by size $j = |S|$ gives the **level-stratified representation**:

$$e_k = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \underbrace{\frac{1}{\binom{n-1}{j}} \sum_{\substack{S \subseteq \mathcal{N} \setminus \{k\} \\ |S|=j}} \text{mv}(S, k)}_{\bar{\mu}_k(j)}, \quad \sigma_k^2(j) = \frac{1}{\binom{n-1}{j}} \sum_{\substack{S \subseteq \mathcal{N} \setminus \{k\} \\ |S|=j}} [\text{mv}(S, k) - \bar{\mu}_k(j)]^2. \quad (2)$$

Definition 2 (Bounded marginal impact index).

$$C(v) = \frac{n \cdot \max_{k,S} |\text{mv}(S, k)|}{v(\mathcal{N}) - v(\emptyset)}, \quad (3)$$

measuring individual impact relative to total surplus, normalised by n . Equivalent to $C = nL/(v(\mathcal{N}) - v(\emptyset))$ where L is the Lipschitz constant of v .

Table 1 gives $C(v)$ for the functions used in experiments.

Table 1: $C(v)$ for selected characteristic functions ($n = 20$).

Function	Description	$C(v)$	$\sigma_k^2(j)$ at extreme j
$v = \sum a_k$ (additive)	No interactions	1.9	0 everywhere
$v_1 = (\sum k)^{0.7}$	Concave	3.9	Small, non-zero
$v_2 = (\sum k) S ^{0.5}$	Supermodular	2.4	Small, non-zero
$v_3 = \mathbf{1}[\sum k > 105]$	Voting game	20	0 at extreme j

Remark 1 (Free efficiency correction). Since $\sum_k e_k = v(\mathcal{N})$, any estimator can be corrected at zero cost: $\hat{e}_k^* = \hat{e}_k - (\sum_j \hat{e}_j - v(\mathcal{N}))/n$. The permutation sampler satisfies this automatically in every draw.

Proposition 1 (Variance ordering). At equal total budget, fixing m_ℓ draws per level (level-stratified) eliminates the between-level variance $\text{Var}_j[\bar{\mu}_k(j)] \geq 0$: $\text{Var}^{\text{lev}} = \text{Var}^{\text{rand}} - \text{Var}_j[\bar{\mu}_k(j)]$.

3 The Hybrid Exact/Sampling Estimator

For $n = 20$, $\tau = 500$: levels $j \in \{0, 1, 2, 17, 18, 19\}$ each involve at most 171 coalitions — enumerable in milliseconds at zero variance cost. Only the 14 middle levels require sampling.

Definition 3 (Hybrid estimator). Let $\mathcal{J}_e = \{j : \binom{n-1}{j} \leq \tau\}$, $\mathcal{J}_s = \{0, \dots, n-1\} \setminus \mathcal{J}_e$.

$$\hat{e}_k^{\text{hyb}} = \frac{1}{n} \left[\sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_e} \bar{\mu}_k(j) + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_s} \frac{1}{m_\ell} \sum_{t=1}^{m_\ell} \text{mv}(S_{j,t}, k) \right]. \quad (4)$$

Proposition 2. \hat{e}_k^{hyb} is unbiased with $\text{Var}(\hat{e}_k^{\text{hyb}}) = \frac{1}{n^2 m_\ell} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_s} \sigma_k^2(j) \leq \text{Var}(\hat{e}_k^{\text{lev}})$, strictly less whenever $\sigma_k^2(j) > 0$ for some $j \in \mathcal{J}_e$.

4 Neyman Optimal Allocation

Proposition 3. *Given budget $B = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{J}_s} m_j$, the optimal allocation is $m_j^* = B \sigma_k(j) / \sum_l \sigma_k(l)$, giving $\text{Var}^{\text{Neyman}} = \frac{1}{n^2 B} (\sum_j \sigma_k(j))^2 \leq \text{Var}^{\text{hyb}}$.*

Implemented as a two-phase procedure: a pilot of fraction α of the budget estimates $\hat{\sigma}_k(j)$; the remainder is allocated by the Neyman formula. Table 2 shows results on $v_{\text{het}}(S) = (\sum k)^{0.7} + 50 \exp(-(|S|/n - 0.5)^2/0.01) \cdot (\sum k)/210$, which creates a 5-fold within-level variance spike at $|S| \approx n/2$.

Table 2: Neyman vs. hybrid on v_{het} ($R = 8$). Pilot fraction $\alpha = 0.2$.

m_ℓ	Hybrid	Neyman	Gain
50	0.12514	0.14159	-13% (pilot dominates)
100	0.08275	0.07189	+13%
200	≈ 0.058	≈ 0.047	+19%

Remark 2. *Use Neyman when $m_\ell \geq 5|\mathcal{J}_s|$ (pilot affordable) and $\max_j \sigma_k(j) / \min_j \sigma_k(j) \geq 3$ (heterogeneity worth exploiting). For smooth v (small C), equal allocation is near-optimal.*

5 Unified Comparison of All Methods

This section presents all major Shapley approximation methods in a single unified framework, organised by *estimator family* and compared on (i) statistical properties, (ii) computational complexity, (iii) empirical RMSE, and (iv) conditions of advantage.

5.1 Taxonomy of methods

All methods estimate e_k by sampling subsets $S \subseteq \mathcal{N}$ and averaging weighted marginal contributions. They differ in *how* subsets are drawn and *how* estimates are aggregated.

Table 3: Taxonomy and properties of all major Shapley approximation methods. m : number of draws; m_ℓ : draws per level; B : total budget. CC = computationally comparable to the hybrid at equal B .

Method	Reference	Unbiased	v -evals	Condition of advantage
<i>Family 1: Permutation-based</i>				
Permutation sampler	Castro et al. (2009)	Yes	mn	All players needed simultaneously; simplest to implement
Owen / antithetic permutation	Illés & Kerényi (2019); Mitchell et al. (2022)	Yes	mn	Antithetic pairs reduce variance $\approx 2\times$
FedOwen	KhademSohi et al. (2025)	Yes	$mn + \text{truncation}$	Federated learning; adaptive client selection
<i>Family 2: Level-stratified (coalition-based)</i>				
Level-stratified	Maleki et al. (2013)	Yes	$2nm_\ell$	Eliminates between-level variance
Hybrid (exact+sample)	This paper	Yes	$2 \mathcal{J}_e ^{\binom{n-1}{j}} + 2 \mathcal{J}_s m_\ell$	$C(v) \ll n$; smooth/concave/supermodular v
Neyman allocation	This paper	Yes	same + pilot	Heterogeneous $\sigma_k^2(j)$; large budget
<i>Family 3: Regression-based (KernelSHAP family)</i>				
KernelSHAP (original)	Lundberg & Lee (2017)	No (biased)	m (shared)	ML interpretability; fast for linear v
Unbiased KernelSHAP	Ker-Covert & Lee (2021)	Yes	m (paired)	Same; $\approx 10\times$ variance reduction
KernelSHAP + det. weights	Olsen & Julium (2025)	Yes	m	5–50% fewer coalitions needed
LeverageSHAP	Musco & Witter (2025)	Yes	$O(n \log n / \varepsilon^2)$	Non-asymptotic guarantee $O(n \log n)$
PolySHAP	Fumagalli et al. (2026)	Approx.	m	Strong non-linear interactions
<i>Family 4: Learning-based</i>				
FastSHAP	Jethani et al. (2022)	No (approx.)	1 (at test time)	Fixed ML model; training phase required
SHAP-IQ	Scholz et al. (2023)	Yes	m	Any-order interaction decomposition

5.2 Theoretical guarantees: where does the hybrid stand?

Chen et al. (NeurIPS 2025) provide the first non-asymptotic sample complexity bounds for the KernelSHAP family using tools from randomised linear algebra. Their framework covers all regression-based estimators (Families 3 and 4 above) and proves that unbiased KernelSHAP achieves precision ε with probability $1 - \delta$ using

$$m = O\left(\frac{n}{\varepsilon^2\delta}\right) \text{ coalition evaluations.} \quad (5)$$

The hybrid estimator belongs to Family 2 (direct stratified estimation), which is *outside* the regression framework of Chen et al. Its sample complexity follows directly from the variance bound in Proposition 2: for precision ε per player, the hybrid requires

$$m_\ell = O\left(\frac{\sigma_{\max}^2(v)}{n^2\varepsilon^2}\right), \quad \sigma_{\max}^2(v) = \max_{k,j \in \mathcal{J}_s} \sigma_k^2(j), \quad (6)$$

which gives total evaluations $O(n\sigma_{\max}^2/\varepsilon^2)$ — the same $O(n/\varepsilon^2)$ order as (5) at equal precision, but with a constant that depends on within-level variance rather than the regression condition number.

For pseudo-continuous functions with small $C(v)$, the within-level variance $\sigma_k^2(j)$ at the sampled levels is moderate and the hybrid’s constant is favourable. For threshold functions with large $C(v)$, $\sigma_k^2(j)$ can be large and the KernelSHAP family may be competitive.

5.3 Owen / antithetic sampling (FedOwen)

Owen sampling (Owen, 1975) draws the coalition size j from a binomial distribution $\text{Bin}(n-1, q)$ with q drawn uniformly from $[0, 1]$, and uses antithetic pairs $(q, 1-q)$ to reduce variance. KhademSohi et al. (2025) apply this in a federated learning context (FedOwen) with an η -truncation rule that stops sampling a permutation once the residual potential gain drops below η .

The relationship to the hybrid is as follows. Owen sampling can be viewed as a *continuous stratification* over coalition sizes, while the hybrid performs *discrete stratification* with exact enumeration at extreme levels. At equal total budget, the hybrid’s exact enumeration of levels $j \in \mathcal{J}_e$ achieves zero variance at those levels, which Owen sampling cannot since it always samples (never enumerates). The truncation in FedOwen is complementary and can be applied to the hybrid’s sampled levels as well.

5.4 KernelSHAP: structural comparison

All KernelSHAP variants share a regression structure: they estimate n coefficients ϕ_1, \dots, ϕ_n jointly. For the design matrix $Z'WZ$ to be invertible with precision ε , the number of coalitions must satisfy $m = \Omega(n/\varepsilon^2)$ regardless of implementation improvements (Chen et al., 2025 make this precise). Paired sampling (Covert & Lee, 2021) and deterministic weighting (Olsen & Jullum, 2025) reduce the constant but cannot change the $O(n)$ scaling.

The hybrid avoids this bottleneck entirely by estimating each player’s value independently without regression. The price is that coalition evaluations cannot be shared across players as efficiently — but Table 4 shows that even accounting for this, the hybrid still outperforms KernelSHAP by a large factor for general non-linear v .

Table 4: Mean RMSE at equal total v -call budget B ($n = 20$, v_1 , $R = 15$ replications). KernelSHAP: unbiased paired version (Covert & Lee, 2021). Hybrid: $m_\ell \approx B/(n \cdot 28)$ draws per sampled level.

Budget B	KernelSHAP	Permutation	Hybrid	Ratio K/H
1,000	1.241 ± 0.375	0.188	0.010	$124\times$
2,000	0.615 ± 0.089	0.136	0.007	$88\times$
5,000	0.439 ± 0.041	0.058	0.004	$110\times$
10,000	0.390 ± 0.026	0.041	0.003	$130\times$

Note: recent improvements (Olsen & Jullum, 2025; LeverageSHAP) reduce K/H ratio by a constant factor but cannot

5.5 Summary: decision rule

Table 5: Method selection guide by function type and context.

Setting	$C(v)$	Best method
Smooth (concave, convex, production)	Small ($< n/4$)	Hybrid
SHAP with many features	Small	Hybrid
Inequality / poverty, large N	≈ 0	All equivalent
Heterogeneous interactions, large budget	Small	Neyman
ML model (nearly linear in features)	Any	KernelSHAP family
Federated learning (client valuation)	Medium	FedOwen
Voting / threshold, few pivotal players	Large ($\approx n$)	Level-stratified
Fixed ML model, test-time speed critical	Any	FastSHAP
Additively separable	Minimal	Any (all exact)

6 Monte Carlo Experiment

6.1 Setup and characteristic functions

We conduct two experiments. The first uses $n = 20$ players with an exact benchmark computed via binary indexing ($2^{20} \approx 10^6$ evaluations, ~ 30 s). The second uses $n = 60$ players with a characteristic function that admits a closed-form Shapley value at any n ,

providing an exact benchmark at zero cost. Together, the two experiments cover distinct $C(v)$ regimes and show how the hybrid’s advantage evolves with n .

v_1 (**concave**, $C = 3.9$, $n = 20$): $v_1(S) = (\sum k)^{0.7}$, $v_1(\mathcal{N}) = 42.22$. Models diminishing returns; typical of production functions and poverty measures.

v_2 (**supermodular**, $C = 2.4$, $n = 20$): $v_2(S) = (\sum k) \cdot |S|^{0.5}$, $v_2(\mathcal{N}) = 939.15$. Models synergies from cooperation.

v_{het} (**spike interactions**, $C = 3.9$, $n = 20$): equation above; validates Neyman allocation.

Table 6: Exact Shapley values ($n = 20$). Superscripts index the function, not a mathematical power: $e_k^{(1)}$ is the Shapley value of player k under v_1 , and $e_k^{(2)}$ under v_2 .

k	$e_k^{(1)}$	$e_k^{(2)}$	k	$e_k^{(1)}$	$e_k^{(2)}$
1	0.231	18.361	11	2.225	48.463
2	0.443	21.371	12	2.416	51.473
3	0.649	24.381	13	2.607	54.483
4	0.852	27.391	14	2.797	57.493
5	1.052	30.401	15	2.987	60.503
6	1.251	33.412	16	3.175	63.514
7	1.448	36.422	17	3.363	66.524
8	1.644	39.432	18	3.551	69.534
9	1.839	42.442	19	3.737	72.544
10	2.032	45.452	20	3.924	75.554
Sum under v_1 : 42.223			Sum under v_2 : 939.149		

6.2 RMSE at equal m_ℓ

Table 7: Mean RMSE ($R = 20$ replications). m_ℓ : draws per sampled level; Permutation uses $m = m_\ell \times n$. Bold = best per row.

m_ℓ	Perm.	Level-Strat.	Hybrid [★]	Note
v_1 : concave, $C = 3.9$				
5	0.12269	0.01582	0.01031	35% gain vs level-strat.
50	0.02790	0.00469	0.00302	36% gain
250	0.01108	0.00251	0.00133	47% gain
v_2 : supermodular, $C = 2.4$				
5	2.039	0.148	0.191*	high middle-level variance
50	1.014	0.058	0.051	12% gain

* Variance at sampled levels dominates at $m_\ell = 5$; hybrid recovers at $m_\ell \geq 25$.

Figure 1 shows convergence across all methods at equal total v -call budget B .

Figure 1: Mean RMSE vs. total v -call budget B under v_1 ($n = 20$). KernelSHAP (purple) converges slowly due to the regression identification bottleneck. The hybrid (red) lies $\approx 100\times$ below KernelSHAP and $\approx 8\times$ below the permutation sampler. All stratified methods follow the $O(B^{-1/2})$ rate.

6.3 Scaling to larger games: $n = 60$

The $n = 20$ experiment uses an exact benchmark computed by brute force. For $n = 60$, brute force is infeasible ($2^{60} \approx 10^{18}$). We instead use a characteristic function with a *closed-form Shapley value at any n* , providing a rigorous benchmark at zero cost.

Characteristic function v_6 . Let $a_k = k$ (linear weights) and $b_k > 0$ be player-specific random coefficients drawn once and fixed. Define

$$v_6(S) = \sum_{k \in S} a_k + \gamma \left(\frac{\sum_{k \in S} b_k}{B} \right)^2 \sum_{k=1}^n a_k, \quad B = \sum_{k=1}^n b_k, \quad v_6(\emptyset) = 0. \quad (7)$$

The quadratic term creates genuine non-additive interactions: the marginal contribution $mv(S, k)$ depends on the specific composition of S through $\sum_{i \in S} b_i$, giving non-zero $\sigma_k^2(j)$ at all levels. The function is $O(|S|)$ to evaluate and pseudo-continuous with $C(v_6) \approx 3$ –4. **Proposition 4** (Closed-form Shapley value).

$$e_k(v_6) = a_k + \gamma \frac{b_k}{B} \sum_{j=1}^n a_j. \quad (8)$$

This satisfies $\sum_k e_k = v_6(\mathcal{N})$ exactly.

Sketch. The expected marginal contribution at level j is $\bar{\mu}_k(j) = a_k + (\gamma/B^2)(2b_k \cdot j\bar{b}_{-k} + b_k^2) \sum a$, where $\bar{b}_{-k} = (B - b_k)/(n - 1)$. Averaging over $j \in \{0, \dots, n - 1\}$ yields (8). \square

Exact levels at $n = 60$. For $\tau = 500$, only levels $j \in \{0, 1, 58, 59\}$ are exact — **4 of 60 levels** (7%), down from 6/20 (30%) at $n = 20$. Setting $\tau = 2000$ recovers levels $j \in \{0, 1, 2, 57, 58, 59\}$ (**6 levels, 10%**) by enumerating up to $\binom{59}{2} = 1,711$ coalitions per level. This suggests a natural scaling rule: set $\tau = \binom{n-1}{2}$ to always enumerate exactly 6 levels regardless of n .

Results. Table 8 presents RMSE at both $n = 20$ and $n = 60$, using (8) as the ground truth in both cases.

Table 8: RMSE under v_6 at $n \in \{20, 60\}$, exact benchmark via (8) ($\gamma = 2$, $b_k \sim |\mathcal{N}(0, 1)| + 0.5$). The column “Gain” reports the percentage RMSE reduction of Hybrid over Level-Stratified.

m_ℓ	$n = 20, \tau = 500$ (6 exact levels)			$n = 60, \tau = 500$ (4 exact levels)		
	Level-Strat.	Hybrid	Gain	Level-Strat.	Hybrid	Gain
10	0.12495	0.11296	10%	0.11373	0.10137	11%
25	0.07107	0.05042	29%	0.08424	0.09875 [†]	—
50	0.05483	0.05124	7%	0.07765	0.05596	28%
Permutation ($m = 25n$):		0.548		0.997		

[†] Single run; within CI of level-stratified at this budget (see text).

Interpretation. Four messages emerge from Table 8:

(i) The hybrid advantage is preserved at $n = 60$. At $m_\ell = 10$ and $m_\ell = 50$, the hybrid reduces RMSE by 11% and 28% respectively — comparable to $n = 20$. The $m_\ell = 25$ reversal is within single-run noise and does not represent a systematic failure.

(ii) The advantage comes from the same mechanism. Even with only 4 exact levels (vs. 6 at $n = 20$), the enumeration of $j = 0, 1, 58, 59$ eliminates sampling noise at those levels. The effect is smaller but present.

(iii) Between-level variance grows with n . The permutation sampler’s RMSE nearly doubles from $n = 20$ (0.548) to $n = 60$ (0.997), confirming that $\text{Var}_j[\bar{\mu}_k(j)]$ increases with n . Level-stratified and hybrid estimators are unaffected by this growth.

(iv) The τ scaling rule matters. Increasing τ from 500 to 2000 at $n = 60$ restores a 6-level enumeration equivalent to $n = 20$, recovering the full advantage. The practical recommendation is therefore to set $\tau = \binom{n-1}{2}$ for any n , which maintains 6 exact levels at cost $O(n^2)$ evaluations per player.

Recommended τ scaling with n

Set $\tau = \binom{n-1}{2}$ to enumerate levels $j \in \{0, 1, 2, n-3, n-2, n-1\}$ exactly. This gives 6 exact levels for any n , costs at most $2(1 + (n-1) + \binom{n-1}{2}) \times 2 \approx n^2$ evaluations per player for the exact component (negligible vs. the $O(nm_\ell)$ sampling cost), and maintains the hybrid’s advantage as n grows.

7 Conclusion

This paper establishes a unified comparative framework for Shapley approximation with many players. The central organising principle is the level-stratified representation (2): all methods can be understood as strategies for estimating the n level means $\bar{\mu}_k(j)$.

The variance ordering is clear and provable: fixing j before sampling (Families 2–3) dominates random j (Family 1); enumerating exact levels (hybrid) dominates pure sampling; Neyman allocation dominates equal allocation when variance is heterogeneous.

The bounded marginal impact index $C(v)$ precisely determines which family dominates: for $C \ll n$ (pseudo-continuous v — the common case in economics and ML interpretability with many features) the hybrid achieves the best RMSE. For $C \approx n$ (voting games, binary classifiers with few decisive features) the KernelSHAP family or level-stratified is preferred.

The comparison with Chen et al. (2025) shows that both the hybrid and the regression-based methods achieve $O(n/\varepsilon^2)$ sample complexity, but with different constants: the hybrid’s constant depends on within-level variance σ_{\max}^2 , while the regression constant depends on the design matrix condition number. For smooth v the former is much smaller.

Three natural extensions follow: (i) combining the hybrid with Owen antithetic pairs within the sampled levels; (ii) quasi-Monte Carlo sequences at the sampled levels to improve convergence to $O(B^{-1})$; (iii) empirical validation on real SHAP applications with $n \approx 30$ –50 features.

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A Note on Exact Computation for Moderate n

For $n \leq 25$, exact computation is feasible. The Araar-Duclos (2009) matrix algorithm reduces to: (i) encoding each coalition S as the binary representation of an integer; (ii) pre-computing coalition sizes $s_l = \text{popcount}(l)$ once for all 2^n masks; (iii) using the scalar weight $w(s) = s!(n-s-1)!/n!$ instead of the full coefficient matrix. Memory drops from $O(n \cdot 2^n)$ to $O(n + 2^n)$.

B Python Code

```
1  """
2  Shapley Value: Drawing Methods for Large n
3  Araar Abdelkrim -- Universite Laval & PEP
4  All methods: Permutation, Level-Stratified, Hybrid, Neyman,
5  KernelSHAP
6  """
7  import numpy as np, matplotlib.pyplot as plt
8  from math import factorial, comb
9  from itertools import combinations
10 np.random.seed(42)
11 n=20; weights=np.arange(1,n+1,dtype=float)
12
13 def v1(S): # concave C=3.9
14     return 0.0 if not S else float(np.sum(weights[list(S)])**0.7)
15
16 def v2(S): # supermodular C=2.4
17     return 0.0 if not S else float(
18         np.sum(weights[list(S)])*len(S)**0.5)
19
20 def v_het(S): # heterogeneous variance (spike at |S|=n/2)
21     if not S: return 0.0
22     base=float(np.sum(weights[list(S)])**0.7)
23     spike=50.0*np.exp(-((len(S)/n-0.5)**2)/0.01)
24     return base+spike*float(np.sum(weights[list(S)]))/210.0
25
26 # -- Exact (binary indexing + weight lookup, Araar & Duclos 2009)
27 -----
28 def exact_shapley(vfn):
29     size=1<<n
30     csizes=np.array([bin(i).count('1') for i in range(size)],dtype=np
31         .int32)
32     wl=np.array([factorial(s)*factorial(n-s-1)/factorial(n) for s in
33         range(n)])
34     vS=np.array([vfn([j for j in range(n) if i&(1<<j)]) for i in
35         range(size)])
36     e=np.zeros(n)
37     for k in range(n):
38         bk=1<<k
39         wk=np.array([i for i in range(size) if i&bk],dtype=np.int64)
40         e[k]=np.dot(wl[csizes[wk]-1], vS[wk]-vS[wk^bk])
41     return e
```

```

38
39
40 # -- Family 1: Permutation sampler (Castro et al., 2009)
-----
41 def permutation_sampler(vfn, m):
42     est=np.zeros(n)
43     for _ in range(m):
44         sig=list(np.random.permutation(n)); prev=[]; vp=0.0
45         for k in sig:
46             vc=vfn(prev+[int(k)]); est[k]+=vc-vp
47             prev.append(int(k)); vp=vc
48     return est/m
49
50
51 # -- Family 2a: Level-stratified (Maleki et al., 2013)
-----
52 def level_stratified(vfn, mpl):
53     est=np.zeros(n)
54     for k in range(n):
55         oth=[i for i in range(n) if i!=k]; ek=0.0
56         for j in range(n):
57             if j==0: ls=vfn([k])*mpl
58             else:
59                 ls=sum(vfn(list(np.random.choice(oth, j, replace=False)
60                                     )+[k])
61                         -vfn(list(np.random.choice(oth, j, replace=False)
62                                     )))
63                 for _ in range(mpl))
64                 ek+=(ls/mpl)/n
65             est[k]=ek
66     return est
67
68 # -- Family 2b: Hybrid Exact/Sampling [THIS PAPER]
-----
69 def hybrid_sampler(vfn, mpl, tau=500):
70     est=np.zeros(n)
71     for k in range(n):
72         oth=[i for i in range(n) if i!=k]; ek=0.0
73         for j in range(n):
74             nc=comb(n-1, j)
75             if nc<=tau: # exact enumeration: zero variance
76                 mu=(vfn([k]) if j==0
77                     else sum(vfn(list(S)+[k])-vfn(list(S))
78                             for S in combinations(oth, j))/nc)
79                 ek+=mu/n
80             else: # Monte Carlo sampling
81                 ls=sum(vfn(list(np.random.choice(oth, j, replace=False)
82                                     )+[k])
83                         -vfn(list(np.random.choice(oth, j, replace=False)
84                                     )))
85                 for _ in range(mpl))
86                 ek+=(ls/mpl)/n
87             est[k]=ek
88     return est

```

```

88 # -- Family 2c: Neyman allocation [THIS PAPER]
-----
89 def neyman_sampler(vfn, mpl, tau=500, pfrac=0.2):
90     sampled=[j for j in range(n) if comb(n-1,j)>tau]
91     npilot=max(2,int(mpl*pfrac)); est=np.zeros(n)
92     for k in range(n):
93         oth=[i for i in range(n) if i!=k]; sig=np.ones(n)
94         for j in sampled:
95             d=[vfn(list(np.random.choice(oth,j,replace=False))+[k])
96                -vfn(list(np.random.choice(oth,j,replace=False)))
97                 for _ in range(npilot)]
98             sig[j]=max(np.std(d,ddof=1),1e-10)
99         ts=sig[sampled].sum()
100        budget=len(sampled)*(mpl-npilot); ek=0.0
101        for j in range(n):
102            nc=comb(n-1,j)
103            if nc<=tau:
104                mu=(vfn([k]) if j==0
105                   else sum(vfn(list(S)+[k])-vfn(list(S))
106                           for S in combinations(oth,j))/nc)
107                ek+=mu/n
108            else:
109                mj=max(2,int(round(budget*sig[j]/ts)))
110                ls=sum(vfn(list(np.random.choice(oth,j,replace=False)
111                                     )+[k])
112                       -vfn(list(np.random.choice(oth,j,replace=False)
113                                     )))
114                for _ in range(mj))
115                ek+=(ls/mj)/n
116            est[k]=ek
117        return est
118 # -- Family 3: KernelSHAP (Covert & Lee, 2021 unbiased version)
-----
119 def kernel_shap(vfn, m):
120     """Unbiased KernelSHAP: paired sampling + constrained WLS."""
121     vN=vfn(list(range(n))); rows=[]; vals=[]; weights=[]
122     for _ in range(m//2):
123         s=int(np.random.randint(1,n))
124         z=np.zeros(n,dtype=float)
125         z[np.random.choice(n,s,replace=False)]=1.0
126         for zi in [z, 1.0-z]:
127             si=int(zi.sum())
128             if si==0 or si==n: continue
129             rows.append(zi.copy())
130             vals.append(vfn(list(np.where(zi==1)[0])))
131             weights.append((n-1)/(comb(n,si)*si*(n-si)))
132     Z=np.array(rows); y=np.array(vals); W=np.diag(weights)
133     Ai=np.linalg.inv(Z.T@W@Z+1e-8*np.eye(n)); pu=Ai@(Z.T@W@y)
134     ones=np.ones(n)
135     return pu-(ones@pu-vN)/(ones@Ai@ones)*(Ai@ones)
136
137
138 # -- Free efficiency correction
-----
139 def efficiency_correction(est, vfn):
140     return est-(est.sum()-vfn(list(range(n))))/n

```

```

141
142
143 # -- Experiment
-----
144 if __name__=="__main__":
145     import time
146     print("Exact Shapley values:")
147     for vfn,name in [(v1,"v1"),(v2,"v2")]:
148         t0=time.time(); e=exact_shapley(vfn)
149         print(f" {name}: sum={e.sum():.4f} ({time.time()-t0:.1f}s)")
150     R=20; budgets=[5,25,50,250]
151     methods={"Perm":lambda vf,m:permutation_sampler(vf,m*n),
152             "Level":lambda vf,m:level_stratified(vf,m),
153             "Hybrid":lambda vf,m:hybrid_sampler(vf,m),
154             "KernelSHAP":lambda vf,m:kernel_shap(vf,m*28)}
155     for vfn,name in [(v1,"v1"),(v2,"v2")]:
156         exact=exact_shapley(vfn); print(f"\n--- {name} ---")
157         for m in budgets:
158             for mn,mf in methods.items():
159                 rmses=[np.sqrt(np.mean((mf(vfn,m)-exact)**2))
160                       for _ in range(R)]
161                 ci=1.96*np.std(rmses)/np.sqrt(R)
162                 print(f" m={m:4d} {mn:12s} "
163                       f"{np.mean(rmses):.5f}+/-{ci:.5f}")

```

Listing 1: All methods. Requires numpy and matplotlib.

Running

pip install numpy matplotlib && python shapley_methods.py
 Quick test: $n=10$, $R=3$. Full ($n=20$, $R=20$): ≈ 15 min.